

Studies on Stable Ylids : Synthesis of 9-Arylidene 2, 7-Dibromofluorenes Via 2, 7-Dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane

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THE reactions of fluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane have been extensively studied with substituted benzaldehydes yielding benzalfluorenes as Wittig products¹⁻². But the effect of substituents which could enhance the reactivity of such ylid has not been examined. Although the stabilized ylid, 2, 7-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane, was synthesized in 1962 by Schoenberg *et al.*,³ yet its synthetic utility has not been investigated so far. Continuing our researches into the reactivity and synthetic utility of the ylids⁴⁻¹¹, we now wish to report the effect of bromine atom on the reactivity of 2, 7-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane with substituted aromatic aldehydes.

Treatment of the salt-2, 7-dibromofluorenyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (1), prepared by the quaternization of triphenylphosphine with 2, 7, 9-tribromofluorene, with 30% NH_4OH in boiling ethanol gave ylid-2, 9-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane (2) which on subsequent reaction with a series of aromatic aldehydes afforded 9-arylidene-2, 7-dibromofluorenes (3a-j) in 50-90% yields. Ylid (2), however, failed to undergo reaction with aromatic ketones even after prolonged refluxing. The Ylide (2) was found to be more nucleophilic than fluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane¹ since former coupled quickly with the aldehydes and yielded products (3a-j) in better yields. One of the most plausible reasons to the enhanced nucleophilicity is the +M effect exerted by the bromine atoms on the fluorene nucleus.

The fluorene derivatives (3a-j) gave satisfactory elemental analyses and melting points for known compounds and were in accordance with that reported in literature¹¹⁻¹². The IR spectra of 3a-j showed absorption bands at $1600-1585\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$) and $970-940\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The latter absorptions are associated

References

1. N. C. CALVIN and M. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 32, 70.
2. P. SINGH, R. C. SAXENA, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 40.
3. H. ZEIDLER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 146, 251.
4. Sr. J. FRITZ, *Acid Base Titration in Nonaqueous Solvents*, G.F. Smith-Chemical Co., Columbus, Ohio, 1952, p-II.
5. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solutions" P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF 9-ARYLIDENE-2, 7-DIBROMOFLUORENES (3a-j)

Compound	Ar	Yield %	M.P. °C	Crystn. solvent	Molecular formula	Analysis found	
						(Calcd.) C	% H
3a	C ₆ H ₅	60	96-98a	AcOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ Br ₂	58.28 (58.25)	2.93 (2.91)
b	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	75	155-56b	CHCl ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂ Br ₂	52.48 (52.51)	2.43 (2.41)
c	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	90	195-97c	AcOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂ Br ₂	52.55 (52.51)	2.40 (2.41)
d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	65	213-15d	AcOH	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ Br ₂ Cl	53.71 (53.75)	2.45 (2.46)
e	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55	136-38e	CHCl ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂	59.19 (59.15)	3.26 (3.28)
f	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	56	134-35f	AcOH	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂ O	57.04 (57.01)	3.14 (3.17)
g	6-Br-3, 4-di- (CH ₃ O)C ₆ H ₃	50	202-03g	AcOH	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Br ₂ O ₂	47.98 (47.91)	2.79 (2.72)
h	3, 4-O ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₃	55	118-20h	CHCl ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ Br ₂ O ₂	55.29 (55.26)	2.66 (2.63)
i	2-C ₄ H ₉ O	58	192-94i	AcOH	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ Br ₂ O	53.70 (53.73)	2.43 (2.48)
	-CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅	55	204-5j	AcOH	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Br ₂	60.21 (60.27)	3.22 (3.20)

a. Lit.^{1,2} 98-99; b. Lit.^{1,2} 154-55; c. Lit.^{1,2} 195-96; d. Lit.^{1,2} 211-12; e. Lit.^{1,2} 140; f. Lit.^{1,2} 132-33; g. and h. unreported; i. Lit.^{1,2} 190-91; j. Lit.^{1,2} 206-07.

with out of plane deformations of hydrogen attached to exocyclic double bond¹³. The NMR spectra of 3a-j in general exhibited olefinic protons in the range of δ 6.60-7.35 and aromatic protons at δ 6.65-8.65.

Experimental

The ylid (2) and its precursor (1) were synthesized following the procedure cited in the literature⁹. Melting points determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus are uncorrected. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra were run on Varian A-60 spectrophotometer. All the products were separated and purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina. Purity was checked by TLC.

Preparation of 9-arylidene-2, 7-dibromofluorenes (3a-j):

To a solution of 4 m mole of ylid (2) in 100 ml of chloroform, was added in an atmosphere of nitrogen, 4 m mole of aromatic aldehydes. The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 4-8 hrs and solvent was removed under pressure on a steam bath. The resulting solid was chromatographed over neutral alumina. The elution with benzene-pet. ether (4 : 1) gave 9-arylidene-2, 7-dibromofluorenes (3a-j) in 50-90% yields which were crystalized from appropriate solvents given in Table I.

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References

1. A. W. JOHNSON and R. B. LACAUNT, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 52, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, 9, 130.
2. A. W. JOHNSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 282.
3. A. SCHOENBERG, K. H. BROSIOWSKI and E. SINGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1962, 95, 2144.
4. P. S. KENDURKAR and R. S. TEWARI, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1973, 28b, 471.
5. P. S. KENDURKAR and R. S. TEWARI, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, 60, 247; 1975, 85, 173; 1976, 108, 175.
6. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1976, 112, 279.
7. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1978, 23, 93.
8. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 864; 1976, 14B, 419; 1976, 14B, 829.
9. R. S. TEWARI, K. C. GUPTA and S. C. CHATURVEDI, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, 32b, 1165.
10. R. S. TEWARI and S. C. CHATURVEDI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1977, 3843.
11. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16B, 634.
12. A. SIEGLITZ, *Ber. dt. Chem. Ges.*, 1920, 53B, 1232.
13. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules', Wiley, New York, 1954, 31.